

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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PU - Public, fully open

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Data Management Plan

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1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Yes. Data provided by some of the participants (including published data) and stakeholders will be used for developing improved models for fiscal metering in WP4. Furthermore, in task 2.1 data about flow metering from previous EMPIR projects will be collected, processed and curated and made available for research purposes.
2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Measured data and associated uncertainties; typically, American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII) and Excel format. Data formats are chosen that are supported by Open-Source software, or software from different vendors to maximise the update of data sets by other groups.
3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Data are generated and used for different purposes. In WP1, WP2, and WP3, most of the data generated during the development of novel facilities and measurement standards will be used to demonstrate their capabilities and assess their performance. The data generated are obtained in the comparisons planned in WP2 (e.g., flow measurement of hydrogen-enriched natural gas and hydrogen) and WP3 (e.g., humidity, sulfur amount fraction in hydrogen) to support calibration and measurement capabilities. Datasets were generated in deliverables and peer-reviewed papers. The data will be used in meeting the project's objectives and in conference and peer-reviewed publications.
4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The datasets are up to a few hundred kbytes, but for metering data, especially from natural gas (task 4.3), a larger dataset was obtained (a few megabytes).
5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Generated data are experimental data (WP1-WP3), and in WP4, predominantly processed experimental data and synthetic (simulated) data. In WP4 it is anticipated to rely on data from gas metering stations (tasks 4.3 and 4.4). Re-used data will come from previous EMPIR projects e.g., 16ENG01 MetroHyVe, 18NRM06 NEWGASMET, 19ENG03 MefHySto, 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2, 20IND10 Decarb, 20IND11 MetHyInfra, and 20IND13 SAFEST.
6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	The data will be useful to JCGM, ISO and CEN technical committees, accreditation bodies, research institutes, calibration and testing laboratories, regulators, and industry.

1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?	Yes. Published data will have a DOI obtained from an open access repository. In all cases, this is the DOI of the document in which the data is presented/used.
8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	<p>The metadata will be rich, so that data sets are stand alone. For orientation, the requirements in standards, scientific journals etc. are applied with respect to the quantities, symbols, units and auxiliary data (e.g. temperature, pressure) is provided as necessary. In principle, the reuse of the data will not require the intervention of the submitter.</p> <p>The metadata created for all of the project's deposited datasets will be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); the European Partnership on Metrology funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.</p>
9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?	Keywords will be provided to enhance the discovery of the data by search engines. The following keywords may be provided: natural gas, hydrogen, metrological traceability, measurement uncertainty, flow measurement, gas quality, composition measurement, temperature, pressure. Keywords will be selected for individual datasets based on their topic area.
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes, Zenodo is used as platform to publish research data and associated documentation. Zenodo complies with FAIR principles (https://about.zenodo.org/principles/). The metadata are indexed in a searchable resource. Metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	Yes. The data and associated metadata, documentation and code will be deposited in the trusted open access repository, e.g., Zenodo (https://zenodo.org). For the software framework, GitHub is used.
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	Yes. From previous experience with, e.g., Zenodo, appropriate arrangements are made. Data sets, their documentation and any computer code can be uploaded without further restrictions in Zenodo. A DOI will be created for easy reference, findability and citation.
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository	Repositories that provide a DOI will be selected. Zenodo is used. The repository will resolve the identifier to a digital object.

Questions	Answers
resolve the identifier to a digital object?	
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	<p>Most datasets created in the project will be made available, usually within reports, deliverables and in peer-reviewed papers.</p> <p>Datasets received from natural gas metering stations are considered commercially and strategically sensitive by their owners and hence may not be sharable. These datasets are most likely to be obtained in support of the work in WP4. If the data owner agrees, these datasets will be made available too.</p> <p>Datasets from surveys will be partially anonymised to protect the privacy of the participants. Such censoring is not expected to reduce the utility of the data.</p>
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	<p>The data used in scientific publications, posters and oral communications will be made available for re-use as soon as is reasonably possible.</p>
16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?	<p>All data associated with the project activities will be made available through a free and standardized access protocol. Zenodo provides well described conditions for free and standardised access (see http://about.zenodo.org/policies/). Exceptions of data not being made accessible are datasets obtained from organisations external to the project consortium. Where possible, permission to release the data will be obtained.</p> <p>Examples containing datasets may be reviewed by reviewers carefully selected by participants and the Data Access Committee (DAC).</p> <p>Some datasets will be released for public access, for example, to end-users of guides and standards, as soon as the data sets are complete, and quality is assured. Other data will more appropriately be made generally available when articles reporting on them are accepted for publication.</p>
17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	<p>No restrictions on the use of the published data are envisaged, but users will be required to acknowledge the project and the source of the data in any resulting publications, according to the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p> <p>As some data have restricted access, access will require a standard user's registration.</p>
18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	<p>Users are required to register to use the repository. If necessary, an authentication system or a data on demand function will be provided.</p> <p>There is no need to ascertain the identity of persons accessing the data.</p>

Questions	Answers
19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	This consortium planned having a DAC. In practice, the tasks of the DAC was taken over by the participants involved in the work generating the data. They addressed, supported the work package leaders and the coordinator, the tasks envisaged for the DAC, They select the data that will be openly accessible on a case-by-case basis. Ethical aspects, the terms of use of the data and data security, including intellectual property requirements, will be considered, as will access requests to personal/sensitive data. If necessary, some or all of a potential publication's data will be withheld. This will be decided in consultation with the relevant participant(s) and, where appropriate stakeholders and collaborators.
Metadata:	
20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, metadata will be made openly available and licensed under CC0 except for email addresses.
21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?	Data stored in the trusted repository will be retained for the lifetime of the repository, which for Zenodo repository, is expected to be a minimum of 20 years.
22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	The data are in a common format and can be read using widely available software (open source or commercial). Therefore, no additional documentation is needed.

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?	<p>Metadata will be provided in accordance with the stipulations of the Grant Agreement. Furthermore, the quantities and units will be provided as well as relevant keywords in the metadata.</p> <p>Vocabularies that will be used include those of ISO and IEC (e.g., ISO/IEC Guide 99 (VIM), ISO/IEC Guide 98-3, ISO 14532, ISO 7504, ISO 80000), IUPAC, and the SI Brochure. Others may be identified.</p> <p>The datasets will use the trusted repository's basic metadata schema for administrative data, which is compliant with the recommended standards used by DataCite (https://search.datacite.org/) and OpenAIRE (https://www.basessearch.net/).</p>
24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you	In the unlikely case that we will need to create our own ontologies or vocabularies, mappings will be created and the vocabularies will be published.

openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow their re-use, refinement or extension?	In deliverable D7, some terms used were defined in a fashion similar to terms in ISO/IEC Guide 98-3. These terms relate to time series analysis and their definitions were developed based on statistical text books on time series analysis.
25 Will your data include qualified references ¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	No, that did not occur. The data sets are self-contained.

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?	Where documentation concerns datasets and code (e.g., scripts), this documentation will be primarily provided in the form of metadata and comments in the script text. A readme file will be provided with each submission describing the parts of that submission. Validation results, where applicable, will also be provided as part of the submission, preferably in PDF, to ensure that this part of the documentation cannot unintentionally be changed.
27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	Yes. The data will either be licensed under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights as set out in the Grant Agreement. Users will be required to acknowledge the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications. Alternatively, the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication License (CC 0) will be used.
28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	Yes. Any data published in open-access journals will be usable by third parties after the datasets have been deposited in a trusted repository. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications will be made available for re-use on a case-by-case basis.
29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	If the data are generated within the project, Yes. Data will be accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. If data are obtained from third parties, the data will be documented so that it can be reused. The provenance of the data may be given in part or not at all to protect the rights.
30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	The quality assurance consists of different layers: (1) The creators of the data will review their data before release. (2) The data will undergo peer review by the consortium prior to release. The participants in the project will be requested to also include the metadata in their review and assess whether the data can be reused without further intervention by the creator or the consortium.

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Questions	Answers
	<p>(3) The submitters will process the comments from the participants and check prior to submission of the dataset once again whether the data are sufficiently self-supporting to be submitted.</p> <p>(4) Peer-review of publications using the data In case of issues with the data set, the coordinator will address these jointly with the creator and issue an improved version of the data set.</p>
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	<p>The estimated costs for making the (data and) other research outputs FAIR are 1 000 € (personnel costs) (see question 34). The costs for making other research outputs FAIR are included in the project's budget and will be claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions. The coordinator will also have overall responsibility for managing other research outputs (see question 36). Where feasible, long-term preservation will be ensured by depositing the other research outputs in repositories.</p> <p>Security of other research outputs All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO/IEC 17025 standard on the "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The participants will store other research outputs on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Other research outputs will also be stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password-protected login. Deposition in public repositories will provide additional security as they have multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. This project will not generate sensitive other research outputs. The other research outputs will be safely stored in open access repositories.</p> <p>Ethical aspects There are issues that could impact on the sharing of other research outputs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information relating to other research outputs acquired from third parties, e.g., manufacturers, will not be shared without their explicit consent. Information relating to other research outputs collected by the consortium at commercial sites will not be shared without the site owner's explicit consent. <p>The project will not share other research outputs with identifiable personal information. Sensitive information relating to the other research outputs will be collected, separated as soon as possible and kept secure.</p> <p>Please also see the information provided in section 1.3 below.</p>

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be	<p>The software developed in the project will be released under a GNU-GPL license.</p> <p>Other research outputs will be managed in a similar manner as the research data. Prior to release, these other outputs are provided to the consortium (Project Management Board) to have informed consent.</p>

Questions	Answers
either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	No physical project outputs are expected to be handled in this manner. The developed measurement standards and methods enable participants to provide outputs as (certified) reference materials or calibrations on request of their customer(s). The management of the IP issues surrounding the new materials that will be developed in the project has been planned for in the project's consortium agreement.
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	Documentary research outputs will be managed and handled in accordance with the FAIR principles. Currently, no project outputs are considered that cannot be disclosed in the course of the project. As far as possible, the FAIR data approaches specified in questions 7-30 above will be applied to the management of this project's other research outputs.

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	The estimated costs for making the data and other research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) are 1 000 € (personnel costs). These costs have been kept to a minimum by using a free repository (e.g., Zenodo) and by making only relevant data and other outputs FAIR.
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	The costs for making the data FAIR are included in the project's budget and will be claimed in accordance with the Grant Agreement's conditions.
36 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	The coordinator will have overall responsibility for data management. He will be responsible for coordinating updates to the data management plan. He will be responsible for organising data backup and storage, data archiving and for depositing the data within the repositories (e.g., Zenodo).
37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?	Long term preservation will be ensured by depositing the data within repositories (e.g., Zenodo). There are no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories.

1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well	All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO/IEC 17025 standard on the "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The participants will

as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	store data on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Data may also be stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password protected login. Deposition in trusted repositories will provide additional security as they have multiple replicas in distributed file systems which are backed up regularly.
39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes. Data will be safely stored in trusted repositories.

1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	<p>Potentially, for data relating to natural gas, hydrogen-enriched natural gas and hydrogen metering data, which may be considered as commercially sensitive.</p> <p>Sharing of these data will be considered jointly with the respective owner(s). Data may be anonymised or not disclosed at all after these considerations.</p>
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	The project has no plans to share data with identifiable personal information.

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	<p>Data will be stored on the Zenodo research data repository, hosted by CERN and receiving funding from the European Commission via the original OpenAIRE Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe and subsequent programmes.</p> <p>Alternatively, similar repositories will be used that meet the applicable objectives and requirements of the European Partnership of Metrology programme</p> <p>Data management will be compliant with the research data policy of the European Partnership of Metrology programme and with European laws regarding data security and the protection of privacy (e.g., General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)).</p>

2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the box to confirm	Or, list any exceptions to this
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	